

ICONICITY AS A COGNITIVE PRINCIPLE IN LITERARY DISCOURSE

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Abstract: The article discusses one type of cognitive principle called iconicity. It is devoted to stylistic analysis of iconicity as a cognitive principle. The article outlines three distinct types of iconicity and their role in forming some cognitive stylistic devices. The article provides literary extracts to illustrate stylistic devices used.

Key words: iconicity, proximity, sequencing, quantity, foregrounding, phonetic iconicity, conceptual information The term "iconicity" refers to the similarity between the verbal sign and its denotate. The issue of the conventionality and motive of linguistic signs serves as the foundation for the notion of iconicity. It is impossible to alter the sequence of homogenous phrases or the logical order of the event sequence. Linguists differentiate between three categories of iconicity.

Both cognitive and stylistic research are very interested in the issue of the iconicity of language signs, which was established in the works of renowned academics such as Peirce, Haiman, Jakobson, Lotman, Eco, Kibrik. The semiotic theory of language's creator, C. Peirce, distinguished three categories of iconic signs—image, metaphor, and diagram—that indicate the relationship between the signified and the signifier based on similarities. From a cognitive-stylistic standpoint, metaphorical and figurative depictions of iconicity are particularly intriguing. We must stress that metaphorical representations of iconicity in our work are generally understood to mean iconicity expressed through all figurative language, including phraseological units, derived and compound words, and stylistic techniques for generating imagery (metaphor, metonymy, antonomasia, allusion, symbol, metaphorical epithet, and metaphorical paraphrase).

In her work, G.G. Molchanova addresses stylistic iconicity in relation to the issue of stylistic device typology. In line with J. Haiman, she makes a distinction between the iconicity of quantity, distance, and sequence and classifies stylistic devices based on these categories. Gradation, zeugma, and phraseological epithet are examples of stylistic elements that are based on the iconic principle of distance. The violation of the concept of sequence serves as the foundation for the construction of stylistic devices such as chiasmus and inversion. All forms of parallelism, antithesis, and repetition are infused with the principle of quantity¹.

The study by N.M. Dzhusupov, which focusses on the cognitive-stylistic analysis of the foregrounding strategy in discourse, also looks at the cognitive principle of iconicity. N.M. Dzhusupov claims that many of the foregrounding strategies, which the author views as involving parallelisms and language deviations, are founded on the principle of iconicity, suggesting a relationship between foregrounding and the cognitive principles of iconicity².

The iconic sequencing principle. It demands that the events in the text match those that actually happened. As an example, the text's overall phrase structure should follow a chronological sequence of events. It deals with the spatial, causal, and socially conditioned regularities of the text organisation that represent the actual occurrences in addition to chronological regularities. The iconic sequence principle

(He arrived, he saw, he conquered) provides the foundation for linguistic phenomena including word order, tenses, and successive phrase structure in the text³.

It should be mentioned that this rule may be wilfully broken in a literary work. G.G. Molchanova highlights stylistic phenomena that defy the text's logical sentence structure, including retrospection, propection, represented speech, and stream of consciousness⁴. Such stylistic strategies as inversion and chiasmus, which position the inverted elements in "the active zone," are based on the breach of conventional word order. R. Langacker coined this phrase, which refers to the activation of the meanings' most conceptually significant subparts.

The violation of iconic sequencing can be seen clearly in the novel "The sound and the fury" by William Faulkner. The main character in the novel is a disabled man Benjy. The story opens with his narration of past events which requires reader's reconstruction of events and chronological orders of them. The writer uses this iconic sequencing in violated form so that he can illustrate Benjy's subjective perception of time, but emphasizing inner consciousness over objective chronology. This was deliberately used by the author as a stylistic and cognitive tool and was so common in Modernist literature. The following extracts from the novel will illustrate this:

"Caddy smelled like trees. We played in the branch and Caddy smelled like trees."⁵...

"Caddy was walking. Then she was crying. She was in the swing. Then Father died."⁶

Following the volumetric-pragmatic segmentation principles, which state that the principle of distance governs segmentation, is essential to the iconicity principle. This indicates that linguistic units are either near or far from one another, depending on the level of semantic relatedness. The author's aesthetic aims define deliberate transgressions of the iconic principle of distance, which help to generate new conceptual interpretations. For example, "The Sick Rose" by William Blake contains following lines which can be seen iconic proximity in: O Rose, thou art sick!

The invisible worm That flies in the night In the howling storm, Has found out thy bed Of crimson joy; And his dark secret love Does thy life destroy.⁷ In the line "Has found out thy bed/ Of crimson joy;" the words "bed" and "crimson joy" are places close as they are conceptually linked. "bed" symbolizes intimacy, and "crimson joy" represents passion and love. The following lines put two opposite concepts against each other: "love" and "destroy" to form paradox: what should bring joy instead causes a destruction. The linguistic closeness reflects the conceptual contradiction and tension at the heart of the author. The foundation of the iconic principle of quantity is the idea that the quantity of verbal cues determines informativity. "More form - more meaning; less form - less meaning" is one way to put it⁸. The issue of redundancy, which is also seen to

be one of the cognitive principles of textual information presentation, is related to this principle. We'll talk more about the redundancy issue. Reduplication, all forms of repetition, phonetic devices (onomatopoeia, alliteration), paronymic attraction, periphrasis, and parallel constructions are just a few of the language phenomena that are founded on the famous principle of quantity.

Clear example can be seen in the "Bleak house" by Charles Dickens. Opening paragraph of the novel starts as follows: "Fog everywhere. Fog up the river, where it flows among green aits and meadows; fog down the river... Fog on the Essex marshes, fog on the Kentish heights. Fog creeping into the cabooses of collier-brigs... Fog in the eyes and throats of ancient Greenwich pensioners..."⁹ Dickens illustrates how the word fog permeates every part of London with a lengthy list and repetition. A sense of immensity, suffocation, and social paralysis are produced by the length and accumulation of details. The fog becomes more intrusive and suffocating the more words are used in the description; this aligns the reader's perspective with that of the protagonists.

It is possible to intentionally employ the iconic principle of number in speaking acts and literary compositions. It serves a number of purposes: a) to draw the reader's or listener's attention; b) to emphasise the redundant element; c) to understand the politeness principle; d) to affect the reader emotionally; and e) to function as the literary text's motive¹⁰.

The iconic signs that function as the text's overall semiotic dominant are the most intriguing feature in terms of foregrounding interpretation. Let's take phonetic conicity as an example, whose importance cannot be overstated. In this sense, E. Poe's poem "The Bells" is a classic example.

Hear the sledges with the bells
Silver bells!

What a world of merriment their melody foretells!
How they tinkle, tinkle,
tinkle, In the icy air of night!

While the stars that oversprinkle
All the heavens, seem to twinkle
With a crystalline delight;
Keeping time, time, time,
In a sort of Runic rhyme,
To the tintinabulation that so musically wells
From the bells, bells, bells, bells,
Bells, bells, bells
From the jingling and the tinkling of the bells¹¹.

Rich in iconic signs, this poetry piece uses paronymic appeal (tinkle - twinkle - oversprinkle), alliterations, onomatopoeias (tinkle, tintinabulation, jingling, tinkling), and repeats of sounds [t], [b], [m], among others to create a sound image of silver bells. The phenomena known as "a phonetically motivated connection between phonemes and the non-sound (non-acoustic characteristic) of the denotatum (the motive) underlying the nomination" should be highlighted in particular. According to this definition, sound symbolism is based on certain motivated linkages between the signifier and the signified in terms of form, movement type, size, etc., even though it is not an imitation of sound.

The contextual characteristics of the use of the lexemes time and bells in this example condition the sound symbolism. These lexemes, when employed repeatedly, produce new kinetic meanings, giving the impression that the bells are swinging rhythmically due to the movement of the harnessed sleds. The reader is deeply affected emotionally and aesthetically by the combination of all the distinctive signals that paint a clear picture of a winter environment, complete with sleds sliding across the snow, horses pulling them, and the glittering ringing of bells. Thus, the text's semiotic dominant is phonetic iconicity.

To sum up, it's critical to stress that the iconicity of foregrounding is defined by: a. The relative, conditional nature of likeness between the fictitious and real worlds within the antithesis of "fictionality - factuality"; b. The artistic

representation of real reality based on relationships of similarity and resemblance between the author's imagined world and true reality; c. Iconic verbal cues in foregrounding: a) help create new conceptual meanings that are emotional-expressive in nature, and b) are important in the process of foregrounding conceptualisation and interpretation.

In conclusion, it is clear that iconicity as cognitive principle can be bases for several stylistic devices to form conceptual and cognitive effect. The study of iconicity can reveal cognitive basis of some stylistic devices which can prove the cognitive features of modern stylistics developed under the effect of anthropocentric paradigm.

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